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Indonesian and Western Pacific bycatch in SSF and bycatch reduction technology testing

Data Set (DS) | Pacific Islands Fisheries Science Center (PIFSC)

GUID: gov.noaa.nmfs.inport:47725 | Updated: December 3, 2025 | Published / External

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Short Citation: [Full Citation Examples](#)

Pacific Islands Fisheries Science Center, 2026: Indonesian and Western Pacific bycatch in SSF and bycatch reduction technology testing, <https://www.fisheries.noaa.gov/inport/item/47725>.

Item Identification

Title: Indonesian and Western Pacific bycatch in SSF and bycatch reduction technology testing

Status: On Going

Abstract: Evidence suggests that Indonesian and Filipino coastal waters provide important foraging grounds for several sea turtle species important to U.S. Western Pacific managed areas and ESA recovery mandates. Continued bycatch and persistent direct harvest of sea turtles in these waters are most likely important factors in the declines of many marine turtle populations in the Pacific such as the Pacific leatherback (*Dermochelys coriacea*), green (*Chelonia mydas*) (i.e. Central Western Pacific and Central South Pacific distinct population segments (DPSs), Western Pacific hawksbill, and olive ridley (*Lepidochelys olivacea*) sea turtle populations. Characterizing the extent, understanding the dynamics driving these practices, and developing mitigation strategies are of great interest as recent genetic and telemetry studies indicate connectivity between sea turtles in Indonesia and the Philippine waters and sea turtles found in US EEZs.

NOAA-PIFSC currently works in partnership with Indonesia's Ministry of Marine Affairs and Fisheries (KKP), WWF-Indonesia (Fisheries Program), and Bogor University to characterize sea turtle bycatch in the small scale coastal gillnet fisheries of the Indonesian Archipelago. This partnership looks to establish a region-wide understanding of fisheries bycatch in these coastal Indonesian fisheries as well as bycatch mitigation strategies useful in these fisheries.

NOAA-PIFSC also has partnered with Philippine's BFAR, DENR-BMB, Palawan Council for Sustainable Development (PCSD), the NGO (LAMAVE), and regional fishery experts to initiate a characterization of sea turtle and other marine megafauna bycatch in the Filipino archipelago.

Purpose: Characterizing bycatch in small scale fisheries and the development of bycatch reduction technology

Keywords

Theme Keywords

Thesaurus	Keyword
UNCONTROLLED	
None	bycatch
None	FRMD
None	gillnets
None	IFP
None	PIFSC
None	rapid assessments
None	sea turtles
None	small-scale fisheries

Spatial Keywords

Thesaurus	Keyword
UNCONTROLLED	
None	Indonesia

None

Philippines

Physical Location

Organization: Pacific Islands Fisheries Science Center

City: Honolulu

State/Province: HI

Country: USA

Data Set Information

Data Set Scope Code: Data Set

Data Set Type: MS Excel Spreadsheet

Maintenance Frequency: None Planned

Maintenance Note: Complete

Data Presentation Form: Table (digital)

Support Roles

Data Steward

CC ID: 596549

Date Effective From: 2017-11-01

Date Effective To:

Contact (Person): Wang, John H

Address: 1845 Wasp Blvd.
Honolulu, HI 96818
USA

Email Address: john.wang@noaa.gov

Phone: (808)725-5370

Distributor

CC ID: 596547

Date Effective From: 2017-11-01

Date Effective To:

Contact (Organization): Pacific Islands Fisheries Science Center (PIFSC)

Address: 1845 Wasp Blvd.
Honolulu, HI 96818
USA

Email Address: pifsc.info@noaa.gov

Phone: 808-725-5360

URL: <https://www.pifsc.noaa.gov>

Business Hours: 8:00 a.m. - 4:30 p.m.

Metadata Contact

CC ID: 900402

Date Effective From: 2019-01-01

Date Effective To:

Contact (Person): Wang, John H

Address: 1845 Wasp Blvd.
Honolulu, HI 96818

USA

Email Address: john.wang@noaa.gov

Phone: (808)725-5370

Point of Contact

CC ID: 596548

Date Effective From: 2017-11-01

Date Effective To:

Contact (Person): Wang, John H

Address: 1845 Wasp Blvd.
Honolulu, HI 96818
USA

Email Address: john.wang@noaa.gov

Phone: (808)725-5370

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Extents

Currentness Reference: Ground Condition

Extent Group 1

Extent Group 1 / Geographic Area 1

CC ID: 596545

Description: Indonesia and Philippines

Extent Group 1 / Time Frame 1

CC ID: 596544

Time Frame Type: Continuing

Start:	2015-01-01
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Access Information

Security Class: Sensitive

Data Access Procedure: Send written request to PIFSC.

Data Access Constraints: At a minimum will require signing a PIFSC non-disclosure statement for fisheries confidential data.

Metadata Access Constraints: none

Metadata Use Constraints: none

Data Quality

Quality Control Procedures Employed: QC review prior to data entry. Further QC after data entry.

Data Management

Have Resources for Management of these Data Been Identified?: Yes

Approximate Percentage of Budget for these Data Devoted to Data Management: Unknown

Do these Data Comply with the Data Access Directive?:	Yes
Is Access to the Data Limited Based on an Approved Waiver?:	Yes
If Distributor (Data Hosting Service) is Needed, Please Indicate:	No
Approximate Delay Between Data Collection and Dissemination:	1 year
Actual or Planned Long-Term Data Archive Location:	To Be Determined
If To Be Determined, Unable to Archive, or No Archiving Intended, Explain:	NCEI-MD does not accept sensitive data at this time
Approximate Delay Between Data Collection and Archiving:	unknown
How Will the Data Be Protected from	Data owner performs regular scheduled back-ups.

Accidental or Malicious

Modification or Deletion Prior to Receipt by the Archive?:

Lineage

Lineage Statement:

Data was collected in collaboration with Indonesian and Filipino governmental agencies, NGOS, Academic institutions, and NOAA and entered in table format into electronic spreadsheets.

Catalog Details

Catalog Item ID: 47725

GUID: gov.noaa.nmfs.inport:47725

Metadata Record Created By: John H Wang

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Metadata Record Last Modified By: SysAdmin InPortAdmin

Metadata Record Last Modified: 2025-12-03 01:00+0000

Metadata Record Published: 2025-02-20

Owner Org: PIFSC

Metadata Publication Status: Published Externally

Do Not Publish?:	N
Metadata Last Review Date:	2020-03-19
Metadata Review Frequency:	1 Year
Metadata Next Review Date:	2021-03-19

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Release 6.0.5

Build FINAL (2025-12-02 18:25 UTC)

